

AN EVALUATION OF THE IMPACT ON INVESTMENT OF FOREIGN DIRECT ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study applies the two-stage least squares (2SLS) method of the simultaneous equation model to investigate the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria from 1994 to 2024. The results of the study showed that, as a result of insufficient FDI flow into the Nigerian economy, there was a negative association between economic growth as measured by GDP and FDI. Therefore, it is advised that Nigeria promote domestic investment to boost economic growth rather than depending solely on foreign direct investment (FDI) as a prime mover. Additionally, a code of conduct for FDI should be developed to stop multinational corporations' restrictive business practices and restrict their ability to repatriate profits from Nigeria.

Keywords: Nigeria, Sustainable Development Goals, Economic Growth, Foreign Direct Investment.

OVERVIEW

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a way for enterprises, investments, and foreign aid from developed nations to generate foreign reserves in most developing nations. FDI is regarded as an important source of capital formation, technology transfer, and know-how, as well as a practical means of international trade Ajiteru, (2018). The inventions and ideas can also be transferred to the receiving countries Nigeria included thanks to the spillover effect. Although it is unclear if faster growth is necessary to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, cross-border commerce is essential for economies to experience equitable and sustainable development (UNCTAD,2019).

Nigeria is currently the first and third host economy on the continent of Sub-Saharan Africa for foreign direct investment. Lately, Nigeria has seen several trade initiatives designed to diversify the economy away from oil-related income. These measures, which naturally lead to austerity, are aimed at enhancing the industrial sector. The government received approximately USD 1.9 billion in foreign direct investment (FDI) in total in 2018, down from USD 3.5 billion in 2017. This decline was attributed to the austerity measures implemented in 2018. By the third quarter, Just 3.37%, or USD 200.08 million, of the entire capital inflow during 2019 came from foreign direct investment Sulaiman, (2024).

According to this theory, foreign direct investment (FDI) is traditionally intended to enhance recipient economies, promoting economic growth and development. As a result, many developing nations draw in FDI in the hopes of bolstering their economies by expanding their portfolio of overseas investments. There is debate because the majority of empirical research

on FDI's effect on economic growth suggests otherwise. Based on extant literature, certain empirical findings indicate a negative correlation between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth. Conversely, other findings suggest that increased FDI leads to a rise in output productivity, hence establishing a positive association between the variables (Emmanuel, 2016). Therefore, by examining the consequences of FDI on the owner as well as the host country using Nigeria as a case study this study adds to the body of current work Abalaka, (2024).

1. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Nigeria's inadequate macroeconomic framework is the reason for the low performance of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the country. The primary factor for foreign investments' success in the nation is mostly driven by the push and pull elements and is influenced by the market size, human capital, and stable macroeconomic environment. Although not significant, FDI has a favorable impact on output, indicating that it has not had a good impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Despite the numerous reforms, the country's proportion of global FDI remains negligible, according to Akanegbu & Chizea (2017). The study used the Ordinary Least Square estimation technique to determine the impact of FDI on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1994 to 2024 and the neoclassical production function (where FDI, capital, and labor are all taken as production inputs). The result shows a positive but insignificant impact of FDI on output productivity in Nigeria Sulaiman, (2024).

Examining the degree to which foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows impact economic growth in Nigeria, (Egbo, 2020), which employed the OLS estimate technique and annual secondary data covering the years 1994–2024, revealed a favorable association between FDI and growth. Furthermore, (Emmanuel,2016) used time series data spanning 1994 to 2024 and several regression estimation approaches to find a statistically significant positive association between FDI and GDP growth. FDI positively and significantly affects Nigeria's GDP in the near term, according to a study conducted utilizing yearly secondary data from 1994 to 2024 was calculated using the Granger causality test and the Error Correction Model (ECM).Ogiemudia & Uwubanmwun, 2016).

In contrast to other capital inflows into the nation, FDI is responsible for a considerable portion of the volatility in Nigeria's economic growth, according to a more recent analysis by Anteror (2019). Modeled utilizing quarterly data from 1961Q1-2016Q4, the Structural Vector Autoregression model was employed.

(SVAR), to assess how private capital inflow shocks affect the expansion of the Nigerian economy. The outcome demonstrates that FDI and portfolio investment shocks have a statistically significant, beneficial, and direct impact on Nigeria's economic growth Sulaiman, (2024).

Further empirical data shows that FDI and production productivity in Nigeria are positively correlated. Using secondary data for the years 1994–2024, (Akiri, Vehe, & Ijuo, 2016) added to the discussion. The VECM's findings demonstrate a sizable positive impact of FDI on

economic growth in Nigeria. FDI also contributes to economic growth in Cambodia. Sokang (2018) conducted a study to examine the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Cambodia. The study used annual time series data from 1994 to 2024 and analyzed the data using multiple regression and a correlation matrix. The results indicated a positive relationship. Using time series data and multiple regression techniques, Gudaro, Chhapra, and Sheikh (2017) obtained the same result for the period 1994–2024 in Pakistan. (Melynk, Kubatko, & Pysarenko, 2014) used panel data on annual transition report indicators from 1998 to 2010 and the Fixed-Effects estimator to analyze the data to conclude that FDI had a favorable impact on economic growth in the nations that were going through the communist transition Abalaka, (2024).

While foreign direct investment (FDI) has a positive effect on economic growth in the near term in many developing countries under evaluation, it hurts growth overall. Using VECM and FULLY MODIFIED OLS (FMOLS) to analyze the short- and long-term effects of FDI on economic growth in developing countries (lower-middle income group) for the years 1994 - 2024, researchers tested the effect of FDI on both short- and long-term economic growth in developing countries (Trang, Duc, Anh, & Thang, 2019). There is some convergence in Portugal between the nation and its trading partners. Panel data research (LEITAO & RASEKHI, 2018) indicates that bilateral trade and FDI boost economic growth. However, research conducted by Umeora (2021) reveals that FDI does not adhere to the theoretical and a-priori expectations that FDI and economic growth are positively correlated. Contrary to previous findings, it was determined using secondary data from 1994 to 2024 and a model that was regressed using multiple regression and OLS techniques that FDI had a negative influence on economic growth in Nigeria Ajiteru, (2018).

2. CONCEPTUAL STRUCTURE

The majority of developing nations receive their investments from local or foreign sources. One type of foreign investment is foreign direct investment (FDI), which is made by foreign multinational corporations (MNCs) with headquarters in developed nations. The Harrod-Domar theory of growth, which holds that any economy must save and invest a percentage of its GDP to develop, lends credence to this study. Stated differently, the A nation's capital-output ratio and amount of savings determine its rate of economic growth Sulaiman, (2024).

In particular, in the absence of government intervention, the growth rate of the national income is inversely or negatively correlated with the capital-output ratio, i.e., a rise in capital lowers the GDP growth rate, and positively/directly correlated with savings and investment, where a higher savings rate increases growth. According to the Harrod-Domar growth model, poor capital formation leads to low savings and investment, which is the fundamental barrier to growth. However, this theory is criticized primarily for being a necessary but insufficient condition for growth. While it is a necessary starting point for growth, it is insufficient to propel it Ajiteru, (2018).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Specification of the Model

The research paper's model is adapted from Balasubramanyam's (2016) work, adding variables including inflation, foreign debt, exchange rate, and a political dummy.

The production function framework developed by Solow, which has been widely utilized to examine the factors influencing growth in developing nations, served as the model's inspiration Sulaiman, (2024).

Testing the theories entails estimating a function that connects the growth of factor inputs to the growth of aggregate output as well as a variable that reflects the increase of total factor productivity.

The following fundamental neoclassical growth equation, which may be expanded to any number of inputs, is the source of the estimated equation (Chenery and Strout, 2016).

$$Q^g - 4^g + b_1K^g + b_2I^g \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where

The rates of total factor productivity, capital, labor, and aggregate output are denoted by the letters Qg, Ag, Kg, and Lg, respectively.

Conversely, the output's elasticity about the inputs is represented by b1 and b2 Abalaka, (2024).

The production approach is a helpful resource for analyzing the input-output connection in developing nations, according to the empirical literature on the subject. The equation is expressed in its general form as follows:

$$Q^g = Q_{t-1} + L^g + Z^g + A_0 + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \times \alpha_3 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

Q^g = Growth rate of real aggregate output

I = Domestic Investment

Q_{t-1} = GDP in Previous Period (Lagged GDP)

L^g = Growth rate of Labour

Z^g = Growth rate of other Variables influencing factor productivity

A_0 = constant term assumed to represent the growth of Productivity.

α_0, α_1 and α_3 = Parameters

The majority of empirical research, including Tyler (2021), Ram (2015), and Balassa (2018), uses the measure Zg to describe how productivity is determined by factors such as inflation, agricultural growth rates, and export growth.

To represent external effects, this article includes foreign direct investment (FDI), outstanding external debts, exchange rates, and political. The Nigerian Naira's power and impact on other foreign currencies Ajiteru, (2018).

The purpose of enhanced production becomes

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INV^g + \alpha_2 EXP^g + \alpha_3 FDI^g + \alpha_4 INF + U1t \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

However, Chete (2018) views the variable representing external influence FDI as also depending on the real growth of gross domestic product (GDP) such that a simultaneous counterpart model to equation (3) can be written as:

$$FDI = b_0 + b_1 GDP^g + b_2 EXR + b_3 EXD + b_4 POD + U2t$$

Where

GDP = Growth rate of GDP

INV^g = Domestic Investment growth rate (Proxy for Domestic Capital Stock

EXP^g = Exports Growth Rate

FDI^g = Foreign Direct Investment growth rate

INF^g = Inflation rate

EXR = Exchange rate

EXD^g = External debt growth rate

POD – Political dummy variable (1 for democratic rule, 0 for military rule).

The a priori expectation patterns of the behaviors of the independent variables in terms of their parameters to be estimated are:

$$\alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \alpha_3 > 0 \text{ and } \alpha_4 < 0 \quad b_1 > 0.$$

$$b_2 < 0, b_3 > 0 \text{ and } b_4 < 0$$

3.2 Estimation Methodology and Data Sources

The two-stage least squares (2SLS) method of simultaneous equation will be used to estimate equations 3 and 4 by the new growth theory, which also endogenizes investment.

The model on the effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria is analyzed using time series data covering the years 1994–2024. Ultimately, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and Financial Review for the various years provided the data that were used Sulaiman, (2024).

4. FINDINGS AND CONVERSATION

The outcomes of the two-staged least squares for the model given in equations 3 and 4 are shown in this section. Equation 3 was employed as a tool for equation 4. Similarly, equation 4 was constructed using equation 3 to capture the other goals of the article, particularly the factors influencing foreign direct investment.

The predicted findings from the 3.1 E-view computer packages are shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2.

Table 1: Two-Stage Least Squares

LOG (GDP)

Method: Two-Stage Least Squares

Sample: 1994-2024

White Heteroscedasticity – Consistent Standard Error and Covariance

Instrument list: Log (GDP)Log (INV) Log (INF) Log (EXR) Log (EXD)POD.

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic
C	11.48757	0.412761	27.83104
Log (FDI)	-0.022700	0.949494	-0.561830
Log (INF)	0.044911	0.031290	1.435322
Log (EXP)	0.053011	0.053966	0.982300
Log (INF)	-0.000563	0.039245	-0.014357
Log (EXR)	0.115738	0.053128	2.178486
Log (EXD)	-0.097545	0.012152	-6.027181
POD	0.073585	0.044046	1.670657
R ²	0.771914	Mean dependent var	11051235
Adjusted R ²	0.69934	S.D. dependent	0.211045
S.E. of regression	0.115721	Sum Squared resid	0 (.294609)
F – Statistic	10.63641	Durbin-Watson Stat.	1.721890

Growth rates were used in a pre-whitening procedure of sorts. The results of the regression analyses, which are displayed in Table 4.1 above, indicate that the explanatory factors explained a total variance of 77% (percent) in the dependent variable (GDP), according to the coefficient of determination R². As a result, the outcome fits well Sulaiman, (2024).

Before all else, exports and domestic investment are showing the anticipated upward trends, implying a direct correlation between them and Nigeria's GDP growth.

This means that *ceteris paribus*, the GDP will rise in response to increases in exports and domestic investment. However, as seen by their t-statistic result in the table, investment proved important while exports were inconsequential.

FDI has been noted to have an adverse indication. This symbol suggests that FDI and GDP have an inverse relationship.

This suggests that FDI negatively affects Nigeria's GDP a sign that Nigeria should exercise prudence when adopting or luring foreign direct investment. This signal, however, might be the consequence of inadequate human capital development, which is the link whereby FDI has little effect on growth.

On the other hand, inflation showed a negative sign, indicating that a drop in the rate of inflation would enhance economic growth in Nigeria. Its t-statistic of -3.205507 indicates that, at the 5% (percent) level of significance, inflation significantly influences growth Sulaiman, (2024).

Additionally, there is a positive correlation between the exchange rate (EXR) and GDP, suggesting that devaluing the Naira will boost GDP growth in Nigeria. The variable's t-statistic score of 2.178486 indicates that it also proved significant at the 5% level of significance.

The external debt (EXD) indicator displayed a negative sign, indicating an inverse or negative association with growth. This implies that increasing debt levels without investing in capital or productive items will hurt Nigeria's economy.

At the 10% significance level, the variable foreign debt is significant, as indicated by the t-statistic value of -1.704660. According to its t-statistic value, the political dummy (POD) also has a positive association with growth and strongly influences it at the 10% (percent) level of significance of 1.670657. This result is better than that of Anyanwu (2018) and Chete (2018). This demonstrates that Nigeria's economic growth will accelerate under a more hospitable democratic regime Ajiteru, (2018).

The model's applicability in ascertaining the presence of a correlation between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic development (GDP) in Nigeria is demonstrated by the F-statistic. The t-statistic value of 10.636441 indicates that the coefficients are jointly statistically significant at the 1% (percent) level of significance, which is further supported by the F-statistic. The model's Durbin Watson (DW) value of 1.721890 indicates the absence of a positive serial correlation Sulaiman, (2024).

Foreign direct investment (FDI) has a negative association with GDP growth in terms of achieving the goal of FDI viability. Table 4.1 presents the empirical result, which suggests that when taking into account total economic growth, FDI may not be feasible for the Nigerian government and private households.

This might be because Nigeria has not developed its human capital to the extent that it could have, through training and imitation, established the links required to realize the spillover impact of new technology between FDI and economic growth. Tables 4.2, which employed FDI as a dependent variable and other elements as determinants, are presented to accomplish the goal of the determinants of the locational choice of FDI Sulaiman, (2024).

Table 2: Determinants of Locational Choice of FDI

Dependent Variable: LOG (FDI) Method:

Two Stage Least Squares

Sample: 1994-2024

White heteroscedecity - content standard errors & covariance instrument list:

Log (GDP)Log (INV) Log (INF) Log (EXR) Log (EXD)POD.

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic
C	3.930091	10.31653	0.380951
Log (GDP)	-0.503476	0.855298	-0.588655
Log (INV)	0.187899	0.362582	0.518224
Log (EXP)	0.539658	0.383881	1.405797
Log (INF)	0.128325	0.126420	1.015071
Log (EXR)	0.514371	0.314934	1.633265
Log (EXD)	0.101502	0.151061	0.671924
POD	-0.342396	0.234116	-1.462506
R^2 0.962809		Mean dependent var 9.078812	
Adjusted R^2	0.544987	S.D. dependent	2.825962
S.E. of regression	108.2507	Sum Squared resid	0 .534241
F – Statistic		Durbin-Watson Stat.	2.026787

Source: Author's Computation

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Source: Author's Computation

Table 4.2 above demonstrates that the explanatory factors explained a total variance of 97% (percent) of the dependent variable (FDI). This indicates that the coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.971786.

Except for Log (GDP), which has a negative value, all the variables have their predicted signs based on past knowledge. This supports the previously stated inverse link between GDP and FDI. This may be the consequence of capital flight brought about by profit repatriation, over-invoicing, or transfer pricing from Nigeria, or it may be the result of insufficient FDI funds infused into the Nigerian economy. Exports, exchange rates (EXP), exchange rates (EXR), and POD are hence locational determinants of FDI, as indicated by their coefficients of 0.539658, Sulaiman, (2024).

The corresponding t-statistics for 0.514371, -0.342396, 1.405797 (10%), 1.633265 (10%), and -1.462506 (10%) are as follows. POD produced a negative signal, despite positive export and exchange rate results. This indication is consistent with Omoniyi and Ibrahim (2019).

In Nigeria, every other factor that was considered a driver of FDI location turned out to be favorable but not significant. Lastly, the DW's value of 2.026787 indicates that the model has no autocorrelation Ajiteru, (2018).

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, contrary to the belief of growth and development experts, the actual results demonstrate a negative association between GDP and foreign direct investment.

This inverse association may be the consequence of insufficient foreign direct investment (FDI) funds invested in the Nigerian economy, which have not had a significant enough impact to improve it or make it more growth-promoting.

Even though GDP and FDI have a negative connection, this does not mean that FDI is a viable option for the Nigerian government or individual households due to the diverse nature of the spillovers.

It was also found that the main locational factors of foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria include exports, exchange rates, and political considerations Sulaiman, (2024).

5.1 Suggested Action

In light of the preceding result, the following suggestions are put forth Sulaiman, (2024):

- i. Instead of depending solely on foreign direct investment (FDI) to propel economic growth, Nigeria ought to promote increased domestic investment.
- ii. Nigeria ought to create a code of conduct for multinational corporations to stop their unfair business practices, restrict their profit repatriation, and make sure a sizeable portion of their earnings are reinvested in the country.
- iii. It is recommended that the government take another look at the demand for local content.
- iv. Nigeria ought to aim for supervised trade liberalization.
- v. Lastly, Nigeria should guarantee the longevity of democratic rule free from unjustified changes to ensure a stable administration.

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Appendix

Follow of FDI in Nigeria 1994 - 2024

	Nominal (NM)	Real FDI (NM)	FDI/GDP (%)
1994	212.5	830.08	0.78
1995	245.5	829.39	0.75
1996	134.4	389.57	0.37
1997	184.3	478.70	0.43
1998	-404.1	-955.32	-0.79
1999	334.7	653.71	0.66
2000	290.0	526.32	0.56
2001	264.3	536.52	0.46
2002	360.4	380.17	0.57
2003	434.1	434.10	0.60
2004	735.8	698.10	1.01
2005	2,553.8	2,199.66	2.25
2006	1,718.2	948.23	1.18
2007	13,877.4	5,088.89	6.17
2008	4,684.0	1,597.54	1.80
2009	6,916.1	2,090.09	2.13
2010	14,463.1	3,023.22	2.63
2011	29,660.3	3,944.71	4.25
2012	22,229.2	1,882.71	2.43
2013	75,940.6	3,721.85	3.84
2014	111,295.0	4,218.76	3.94
2015	110,452.7	3,857.53	3.76
2016	80,750.4	2,564.16	2.80
2017	92,792.5	2,763.66	2.77
2018	115,952.2	3,229.42	2.33
2019	132,433.7	3,192.95	2.35
2020	225,036.5	4,595.40	3.81
2021	258,388.6	4,703.70	2.55
2022	248,224.6	3,608.41	2.13
2023	302,753.4	4,164.05	2.79
2024	573835.0	7,119.89	3.93

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